

Final Report

1 General Information

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Dynamische HPC Softwarepakete: Nahtlose Integration von existierenden Softwarepaketen und Codegenerierungstechniken (Dynamic HPC software frameworks: Seamless integration of existing simulation frameworks and code generation techniques)

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2 Summary

Multiphysics simulations are an important tool in many natural science and engineering fields e.g. to optimize placement of wind turbines or to predict material transport in riverbeds. Such simulations usually require a large amount of computing resources to produce accurate results and are commonly run on a supercomputer. Due to these systems' high power consumption costs, highly parallel and efficient implementations for the numerical schemes and complex coupling methods are required. For application scenarios, experts from various domains have to collaborate, and the underlying codes are often developed and used over many years.

One major issue arises from modern hardware trends towards more and more heterogeneous systems, since developing and maintaining hand-optimized compute kernels for several target architectures and accelerators is very time-consuming in the long term for a multiphysics framework that supports a wide range of different models. Code generation approaches tackle this problem because the definition of the method itself is separated from the description of the algorithm and how to optimize it. Additionally, possible hardware-dependent optimization strategies are automated in the code generation process and applied to an abstract algorithm description. However, in scientific software, code generation technology is still a new technology, so it is essential to evaluate it carefully and critically. Limited experience existed so far in terms of its sustainability and its long-term impact on the development process. Our findings, software tools, and best practices can help to achieve the meta-goal to systematically upgrade existing scientific software with code generation features.

In the project, several code generators for different purposes are coupled with the multiphysics simulation framework waLBerla to design a dynamic framework that fuses manual and generated implementations. The dynamic framework is built on top of open-source tools and uses several different code generation techniques that can be applied to a wide range of simulation codes and architectures. For application scientists it becomes easier to couple simulation tools and to incorporate new models using the provided high-level abstractions that hide implementation and platform details.

Zusammenfassung: Multiphysik-Simulationen sind ein wichtiges Werkzeug in vielen Bereichen der Natur- und Ingenieurwissenschaften, z.B. zur Optimierung der Platzierung von Windkraftanlagen oder zur Vorhersage des Materialtransports in Flussbetten. Solche Simulationen erfordern in der Regel eine große Menge an Rechenressourcen, um genaue Ergebnisse zu erzielen, und werden in der Regel auf einem Supercomputer durchgeführt. Aufgrund des hohen Stromverbrauchs dieser Systeme sind hochparal-

lele und effiziente Implementierungen für die numerischen Verfahren und komplexen Kopplungsmethoden erforderlich. Für Anwendungsszenarien arbeiten meist Experten aus verschiedenen Bereichen zusammen, und die zugrundeliegenden Codes werden oft über viele Jahre hinweg entwickelt und verwendet.

Ein großes Problem ergibt sich aus den modernen Hardware-Trends zu immer hetero-generen Systemen, da die Entwicklung und Pflege von handoptimierten Berechnungskerneln für verschiedene Zielarchitekturen und Beschleuniger für ein Multiphysik-Framework, das eine Vielzahl unterschiedlicher Modelle unterstützt, auf Dauer sehr zeitaufwändig ist. Codegenerierungsansätze helfen, dieses Problem anzugehen, da die Definition der Methode selbst von der Beschreibung des Algorithmus und seiner Optimierung getrennt wird. Außerdem werden bei der Codegenerierung möglicherweise hardware-abhängige Optimierungsstrategien automatisiert und auf eine abstrakte Beschreibung des Algorithmus angewendet. Bei wissenschaftlicher Software ist die Technologie der Codegenerierung jedoch noch relativ neu. Daher ist es wichtig, sie sorgfältig und kritisch zu bewerten. Bislang gibt es nur begrenzte Erfahrungen in Bezug auf ihrer Nachhaltigkeit und ihrer langfristigen Auswirkungen auf den Entwicklungsprozess. Unsere Erkenntnisse, Software-Tools, und Best Practices können dazu beitragen, das Meta-Ziel zu erreichen, bestehende wissenschaftliche Software systematisch mit Codegenerierungsfunktionen zu erweitern.

Im Rahmen des Projekts werden mehrere Codegeneratoren für unterschiedliche Zwecke mit dem Multiphysik-Simulationsframework waLBerla gekoppelt, um ein dynamisches Rahmenwerk zu schaffen, das manuelle und generierte Implementierungen miteinander verbindet. Das dynamische Rahmenwerk baut auf Open-Source-Tools auf und verwendet verschiedene Codegenerierungstechniken, die auf eine breite Palette von Simulationscodes und -architekturen angewendet werden können. Für Anwendungswissenschaftler wird es damit einfacher, Simulationswerkzeuge zu koppeln und neue Modelle mit Hilfe der bereitgestellten High-Level-Abstraktionen, die Implementierungs- und Plattfordetails verbergen, einzubinden.

3 Progress Report

3.1 Background and objectives of the project

Multiphysics simulation codes are often implemented in languages such as Fortran or C++ and use [MPI](#) to run on large distributed-memory HPC clusters. While this enables efficient and scalable codes on most CPU clusters, it is a current research problem how to achieve performance portability on newer HPC architectures like GPUs.

In the case of an existing C++ framework, one approach is to rely on [C++ standard parallelism](#) introduced in C++17. Another approach is [SYCL](#), an abstraction layer over OpenCL. More and more software frameworks also use C++ libraries that provide abstract parallel patterns such as [Kokkos](#) or [RAJA](#) to enable performance-portability across different platforms.

A more flexible approach is to use **Domain Specific Languages (DSL)**. In the context of DSLs, **code generation** refers to the process of automatically producing code in a target language (like C++, Java, Python, etc.) from specifications or models defined using the DSL. The code generation process consists of several steps: defining the DSL syntax, implementing a parser logic, transforming the DSL representation to an intermediate representation (IR), and finally generating target code from the IR. In this way, one can generate optimized versions for different architectures automatically. However, for existing manually implemented multiphysics simulation frameworks, the question arises of how to couple them with generated code.

The **main objective** of our project was to develop methodology and best practices on how to seamlessly fuse modern, massively parallel simulation frameworks and code generation technology. This resulted in a dynamic, parallel multi-platform multiphysics simulation framework containing both hand-written and generated code. These generated codes can be single compute kernels, whole sub-modules like numerical solvers with parallel data structures, communication routines, and also interfaces that establish the coupling of the codes.

3.2 Description of the project-specific results and findings

As an exemplary multiphysics simulation framework serves **waLBerla** [1]. waLBerla is written in C++, uses an octree-based data structure including adaptive mesh refinement and load balancing strategies, and supports a variety of applications centered around computational fluid dynamics using the Lattice Boltzmann Method (LBM). During the project, we achieved the following results:

Further development of existing and new DSLs

As an embedded DSL (eDSL) for LBM, **lbmpy** [2, 3] provides high-level abstractions for LBM models which can then be further propagated to the IR of [pystencils](#), a kernel generation tool for stencil codes with an extended [SymPy](#) as abstraction layer.

To overcome the limits of the [Jinja](#) template-based approach to generate wrapper code, we started to develop a [pystencils](#) Source File Generator ([pystencils-sfg](#)). Here, the user

writes generator scripts, which are translated one-to-one into C++ header/implementation file pairs; this process can be automated by the included CMake module. Inside these scripts, the user invokes `pystencils` to generate kernels and describes the necessary wrapper code with a descriptive API that mimics C++ syntax.

We also built an additional tool upon the `pystencils` technology, the HyTeG Form Generator (HFG), a specialized code generator tailored for matrix-free Finite-Element (FE) operators that can e.g. be coupled to the FE framework [HyTeG](#). HFG places a strong emphasis on optimizing the local evaluation of bilinear forms, employing various techniques such as tabulation, automatic identification, and relocation of loop invariants, along with inter-element vectorization and loop unrolling [8].

ExaSlang is an external DSL integrated into the whole program generation framework **ExaStencils** [4] that specializes in numerically solving PDEs using iterative solvers on block-structured grids.

In [9], we investigate how code generation can be utilized for producing framework interfaces to exploit on-the-fly conversions and data mappings. For this purpose, concepts from the underlying HPC framework are introduced to the code generator, including its abstract input layer, its code generation pipeline, and its back-end. This allows users to work productively on the DSL input layer. Our approach also allows us to fuse additional computations, such as unit conversions and interpolations, into the coupling routines. The emitted code directly operates on existing HPC framework data structures while benefiting from automatic optimizations and parallelization provided by the code generator. We bridge the gap between generated and existing codes via automatically generated interfaces that can then be used by the coupled application.

To support the octree data structure from `walBerla` in the software coupling with generated `ExaStencils` code, various adaptations within the code generator were made to support mesh refinement concepts [10]. This includes the generation of communication routines for neighbors with different refinement levels that can be flexibly augmented with automatic extra- or interpolation schemes. These are used to handle jumps in the resolution and preserve the convergence of the numerical solver.

To enable automatic performance engineering it is possible to use the internal data structures of a code generator to set up a performance model during the generation process. The work in [15] describes the initial development steps of integrating this approach into `ExaStencils`. Throughout the project, we extended this evaluation strategy to support kernels using higher-dimensional data types such as matrices and also use its kernel runtime predictions as a decision criterion if a kernel should be run on the CPU or an accelerator like GPU.

Hand-in-hand with applying several optimization techniques to improve kernel performance, it is advisable to fine-tune algorithmic parameters to further improve the execution time of a simulation. Numerical schemes such as the multigrid method span a search space that exceeds the possibilities of an exhaustive search by hand, which makes machine-learning or genetic programming techniques a promising choice. In [5], a grammar-guided genetic programming approach was used to find optimal solver algorithms for complex Helmholtz application scenarios with respect to multiple objectives such as performance, convergence, etc.

For rigid body particle dynamics, we started with the **MESA-PD** [6] eDSL that provides a Python user interface for specifying particle configurations whose properties are then inserted into annotated C++ files via Jinja templates. Since MESA-PD has limited flexibility and only supports CPUs, we also developed compiler technology for generating efficient particle simulations in the scope of the eDSL **P4IRS** Python module [16]. In contrast to MESA-PD, this compiler approach facilitates providing back-ends for various hardware architectures such as CPUs and GPUs and enables automatic optimizations such as SIMD vectorization. The benefits of code generation are shown in the performance evaluation against MESA-PD and MD-Bench [11], a performance-focused prototyping harness that contains state-of-the-art molecular dynamics kernels implemented for CPU and GPU back-ends.

Dynamic framework design

Figure 1 depicts an exemplary workflow of the coupling process in the dynamic framework for a multiphysics simulation with charged particles in a fluid. We employ ExaStencils to find the solution of the quasi-stationary Poisson equation for the electrostatic potential, lbmpy for simulating the fluid, and MESA-PD for the particle simulation. All of these code generation tools can produce optimized and parallelized target code for various hardware platforms.

Typically, the algorithmic components and their software tools are considered individually. However, multiphysics simulations require data exchange between these components with the help of methods such as the partially saturated cells method (PSM) for the coupling between fluid and particles [12]. These couplings perform mappings between data structures and conversion of physical quantities.

Figure 1: Schematic view on the coupling process of the dynamic framework.

Automatic testing and performance engineering

We established continuous integration (CI) and continuous benchmarking (CB) infrastructures for [walBerla](#) and [ExaStencils](#). CI ensures that the processes of code generation, compilation, linking, and code execution are still successful after a commit to the repository. Beyond a regular validation of our codebases and non-functional behavior such as performance is covered by CB. Our hardware environment is the RRZE [testcluster](#) with a wide spectrum of CPU and GPU architectures available for benchmarking. These pipelines employ tools like [LIKWID](#) to obtain metrics for systematic performance modeling. With these, we can also study the influence of specific optimization techniques for different hardware architectures and compilers. The infrastructure proposed in [7] can be used to concisely formulate benchmarks from diverse application domains, execute them on all available combinations of target architectures and compiler modules, create systematic performance models, such as a Roofline model, and visualize the performance results in an interactive Grafana dashboard in real-time.

Generating full multiphysics applications

We were able to showcase the usefulness and practicability of our dynamic framework approach on a number of real-world applications that solve complex multiphysics prob-

(a) Dilute fluidized bed scenario. (b) Vorticity plot of a wind turbine. (c) Electric force for charged particles. (d) Antidune formation in a riverbed.

Figure 2: Application Scenarios for our dynamic HPC framework.

lems depicted in Fig. 2. On the left-most side, there is a fully resolved particle-laden flow simulation of a dilute fluidized bed application [12]. In this case, different simulation modules are mapped to different subsystems of a heterogeneous architecture. The result is a hybrid implementation with some algorithmic parts being offloaded to the GPU and some remaining on the CPU. The Eulerian representation of the flow utilizes GPUs, while the Lagrangian model for the particles runs on conventional CPUs. This implementation exhibits a parallel efficiency of up to 71% on 1024 A100 GPUs.

Figure 2b shows the vorticity field of an isolated wind turbine. For this simulation, the actuator-line method is used to represent the turbine geometry [13]. The coupling between the turbine and the fluid is then performed via the forces the turbine exerts on the fluid. The entire fluid module is based on waLBerla and kernels generated by pystencils and lbmpy and can address both CPUs and GPUs. This provides a performance-portable solution for single- and multi-turbine simulations.

In [17], we extended the fluidized bed application by the simulation of charged particles. The generated multigrid solver from ExaStencils is coupled to the application via our dynamic framework. This solver computes electrostatic quantities, such as the electrostatic force in Fig. 2c, which are then included in the Lagrangian particle algorithms. The generated interface bridges the gap between the algorithms of the charges, the fluid, and the particles.

Figure 2d illustrates the simulation of supercritical turbulent free surface flow over a polydisperse sediment bed [14]. Here, we employed the free-surface lattice Boltzmann method for the fluid flow and coupled it with DEM for the particle dynamics. Momentum exchange between the fluid and solid phases is also considered. The fluid kernel is

obtained using lbmpy. By reproducing two flow configurations of previous experiments using large-scale simulations on the SuperMUC-NG supercomputer, we demonstrate that our approach is robust and accurately predicts the antidunes' physics.

In [18], we demonstrated the generation of interfaces between generated codes from ExaStencils and the [VisIt](#) tool for interactive visualization and analysis. The implementation of a system with visualization and evaluation routines for the large amount of data generated in production runs of the antidune application is shown in [19].

3.3 Deviations from the original concept

In our proposal, we imagined automating processes like knowledge extraction from existing code or the selection of suitable code transforms to achieve an optimized implementation for a specific architecture. We had already successfully employed different heuristic search strategies in previous projects like ExaStencils [4].

With the latest development in generative AI, however, and the availability of AI-assisted pair programming, we have now started to investigate this direction in more detail. Currently, we foresee a large impact on DSL design and code generation in general, but the technology is not yet mature enough for more complex application codes.

3.4 Activities and approaches to quality-enhancing measures through which the validity or verifiability of your research findings was ensured

We published results in peer-reviewed scientific journals or conference proceedings and validated the numerical results either in collaboration with experts from the application fields or by comparing them to experimental results. The feasibility of performance and scalability results is checked by performance models. Furthermore, under the assumption of access to HPC resources, the computational results are fully reproducible since our software and necessary data are open-source.

3.5 Description of the handling of research data generated in the project and the data infra-structures used

In general, we follow the rules and apply the concepts for research software and data management at [FAU](#). General information and description of our software frameworks, application examples, additional documentation, and tutorials can be found on the websites for [ExaStencils](#) and [waLBerla](#). Open-source access to the software sources

is provided via Git repositories. To be able to cite a specific version in a publication or to store additional data we use Zenodo records. For long-term storage e.g. of larger simulation results we use the infrastructure provided by [NHR@FAU](#).

3.6 Description of any research data, methods, standards, software or infrastructures that are re-usable and openly accessible to others

Our software is available to the public under the GPLv3 license including documentation, tutorials, and a set of examples for various applications.

3.7 Implementation of scientific events, science communication measures

Our group has participated in conferences with scientific talks (SIAM CSE'23), proceeding presentations (IPDPS'23, PASC'23, EuroPar'24), and poster presentations (PASC'22). Among the proceeding presentations, the work in [10] has been invited to the best paper session at the EuroPar'24 conference.

3.8 Bibliography

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4 Published Project Results

4.1 Publications with scientific quality assurance

- [8] N. Kohl, D. Bauer, F. Böhm, and U. Rüde. “Fundamental data structures for matrix-free finite elements on hybrid tetrahedral grids”. In: *International Journal of Parallel, Emergent and Distributed Systems* 39.1 (2024), pp. 51–74.
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4.2 Other publications and published results

- [15] M. Blöcher. “Automated Performance Prediction for Generated PDE Solvers”. Bachelor’s Thesis. 2019.
- [16] R. Ravedutti Lucio Machado, J. Eitzinger, and H. Köstler. “P4irs: An Intermediate Representation and Compiler for Parallel and Performance-Portable Particle Simulations”. Submitted to: *Int. J. of High Performance Computing Applications*. Pre-print on webpage at <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4714072>. 2024.
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- [18] R. Angersbach. “Generating an Interface for Parallel Multigrid Solvers and VisIt”. Bachelor’s Thesis. 2018.
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4.3 Patents (applied for and granted)

N/A